

Attempts to Prepare Dyes from Fluorenone.

BY ANUKUL CHANDRA SIRCAR AND KHITISH CHANDRA BHATTACHARYYA.

Since it is well known that in presence of a chromophoric group, a compact ring structure acts as an additional chromophore, it was thought of exploring the possibility of preparing dyes from fluorenone by taking it as a chromophoric seat and packing other groups round it. With this object in view the present investigation was undertaken. It may be mentioned here that hitherto no dyestuff had been prepared from fluorenone except those described by Underwood and Kochmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 3075).

The $-N=CH-$ group, like the azo-linking $-N=N-$ is known to enhance tinctorial properties (*cf.* Green and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 2242; Morgan and Reeves, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1; Sircar and Sen-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **1**, 321) and successful attempts have been made of creating the azo-methine groups in the fluorenone molecule by condensing various aromatic aldehydes, *e.g.*, benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-acetylaminobenzaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, resorcydaldehyde and vanillin with 2-aminofluorenone, the object being to investigate the effect of azo-methine groups on the colour of the compound.

Fluorenonephenylazo-methines are easily obtained and many of them are fairly deep coloured and form well-defined crystals, but are not satisfactory so far as their dyeing properties are concerned. They possess no affinity for cotton and are decomposed into the original components when boiled for some time with water in presence of an acid. Wool can however be dyed with them from one per cent. acetic acid bath between 80 and 85°. But though the bath is exhausted, even in that case the shades obtained on wool are neither very bright nor very deep. In their properties therefore the fluorenonephenylazo-methines closely resemble the phenanthraquinonephenylazo-methines described by Sircar and Sen-Gupta (*loc. cit.*).

A number of azo-derivatives have also been prepared by coupling 2-diazo-fluorenone chloride with various phenols and amines *e.g.* β -naphthol, dimethylaniline, phenol, salicylic acid, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, naphthionic acid, 1-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid, diethyl-

aniline, R-acid (β -naphthol-3:6-disulphonic acid) and G-acid (β -naphthol-6:8-disulphonic acid).

The fluorenoneazo-derivatives are obtained mostly in well-defined crystalline form and majority of them are deep coloured and possess well-developed dyeing properties. They dye wool evenly from one per cent. sulphuric acid bath in shades ranging from orange yellow to deep scarlet and bluish-violet.

Lastly, an attempt was made to prepare vat dyes from 2-aminofluorenone by condensing it with various dibasic acid chlorides, *e.g.*, oxalylchloride, phthalylchloride, carbonyl chloride, thionyl chloride, malonic acid (in presence of phosphorus pentachloride), succinic acid (in presence of phosphorus pentachloride) and glutaric acid (in presence of phosphorus pentachloride), but contrary to the expectation, the resulting fluorenonylamides could not be made to yield soluble vats with hydrosulphite. They however dye wool, though slowly, from an one per cent. sulphuric acid bath. But the shades obtained, though even, are invariably very light and rather disappointing.

Attempts to apply Ullmann's reaction to 2-bromofluorenone (Schmidt and Bauer, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 764) with a view to prepare anilinofluorenones were unsuccessful in the sense that simultaneously with the bromine atom the ketonic group was also attacked. The resulting products, being therefore of no interest, were not further investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For the preparation of the azo-methines (described in Table A), equimolecular proportions of 2-aminofluorenone and the aldehyde are dissolved in the least quantity of alcohol, except where otherwise mentioned, and the solution heated on the water-bath until the separation of the solid is complete (the time required for the same has been noted in each case). The product is purified by crystallisation. The yield is generally almost theoretical. They are moderately soluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in acetone or chloroform and insoluble in water and have the following general formula:

R = phenyl or substituted phenyl nucleus.

For the preparation of the fluorenoneazo-derivatives described in Table B, 2-aminofluorenone is diazotised (Diels, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1764) and the 2-diazo-fluorenone chloride is coupled with the calculated quantity of the second component in the usual way.

Attempts to prepare Vat Dyes.—The condensation of the dibasic acid chlorides with 2-aminofluorenone is easily effected by heating for about two hours a solution of two molecules of the aminoquinone with somewhat more than one molecule of the acid chloride in nitrobenzene. The reaction takes place in the following way:

The condensation products are precipitated from the nitrobenzene solution on the addition of ether and are purified by repeatedly washing with ether and finally with water. They resist all attempts towards crystallisation, being insoluble in all organic solvents, and are reddish-brown or brownish-red amorphous bodies, not melting below 290°. They cannot be reduced to soluble vats. The compounds obtained are detailed in Table C.

TABLE A
Fluorenone-2-azo-methine Derivatives.

Name.	Method of preparation. A = 2-aminofluorenone.	Appearance and m.p.	Shade of dyeing on wool.	Analysis (nitrogen) Found. % Calc.
1. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine benzene).	A + benzaldehyde (no solvent taken); heating for 3 hours.	Brown needles (from dilute alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Light pink-buff.	5.19 4.94 p.o.
2. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-2'-hydroxybenzene).	A + salicylaldehyde (standing overnight at ordinary temperature).	Orange-yellow needles (from hot alcohol); m.p. 230°.	Pinkish-orange.	4.9 4.68 "
3. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-3'-hydroxybenzene).	A + <i>m</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde; heating for about 10 hours.	Brown needles (from hot alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Pinkish-buff.	49.6 4.68 "
4. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-4'-hydroxybenzene).	A + <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde; heating for 3½ hours.	Deep orange crystalline powder (from hot alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Reddish-orange.	4.92 4.68 "
5. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-2'-nitrobenzene).	A + <i>o</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde; heating for 3 hours.	Deep yellow needles (from hot alcohol); m.p. 152°.	Yellow.	8.91 8.53 "
6. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-4'-nitrobenzene).	A + <i>p</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde; heating for 3 hours.	Orange-red crystalline powder (from hot alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Light yellowish-orange.	8.6 8.53 "
7. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-3'-nitrobenzene).	A + <i>m</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde; heating for 3 hours.	Orange needles (from hot alcohol); m.p. 213°.	Light orange-yellow.	8.9 8.53 "
8. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-4'-acetylaminobenzene).	A + <i>p</i> -acetylaminobenzaldehyde; heating for 9 hours.	Deep red needles (from hot alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Light pink.	8.39 8.28 "
9. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-4'-dimethylaminobenzene).	A + <i>p</i> -dimethylaminobenzaldehyde; heating for 4½ hours.	Deep red crystalline powder (from alcohol); m.p. 256°.	Brownish-yellow.	8.81 8.58 "
10. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-2':4'-dihydroxybenzene).	A + resorcydaldehyde; heating for 4 hours.	Deep scarlet needles (from alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Reddish-orange.	4.61 4.44 "
11. Fluorenone-2-(1'-azo-methine-3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzene).	A + vanillin; heating for 3 hours.	Beautiful scarlet needles (from alcohol); not melting below 290°.	Light pinkish-violet.	4.44 4.25 "

TABLE B.

Fluorenoneazo-derivatives.

Name.	Method of preparation.	Appearance and m.p.	Solubilities.	Shade of dyeing on wool.	Analysis (nitrogen)
	D = 2-diazo-fluorenone chloride.				Found. Calc.
1. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-2'-naphthol.	D + β -naphthol.	Reddish-violet crystalline powder; m.p. 192°-94°	Slightly soluble in hot alcohol, insoluble in acetone, chloroform or water.	Reddish-violet.	8.13 800 p.c.
2. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-4'-dimethylaminobenzene.	D + dimethyl aniline.	Brownish-red crystalline powder (from hot alcohol); m.p. 193°	Moderately soluble in hot alcohol, sparingly soluble in acetone or chloroform and insoluble in water.	Reddish-brown.	13.1 12.84,,
3. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-4'-hydroxybenzene.	D + phenol.	Orange-red powder, (from alcohol); m.p. 213°.	Sparingly soluble in hot benzene or acetone, moderately in alcohol, insoluble in water.	Orange-yellow.	9.56 9.33,,
4. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-4'-hydroxy-3'-benzoic acid.	D + salicylic acid.	Yellowish-orange rectangular crystals; m.p. 216°.	Sparingly soluble in hot alcohol, insoluble in acetone or water.	Yellowish-brown.	8.37 8.1,,
5. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-2'-hydroxy-3'-naphthoic acid.	D + 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid.	Bluish violet rectangular crystals; m.p. above 310°.	Slightly soluble in hot alcohol, insoluble in acetone, chloroform or water.	Bluish-violet.	7.2 7.1,,

TABLE B—*contd.*

Name.	Method of preparation.	Appearance and m.p.	Solubilities.	Shade of dyeing on wool.	Analysis (nitrogen)
					Found. Calc.
6. Fluorenone-2-(2')-azo-1'-naphthylamine-4'-sulphonic acid.	D + naphthionic acid.	Deep reddish-brown rectangular crystals (hot alcohol); m.p. above 310°.	Moderately soluble in hot alcohol or acetone, slightly soluble in hot water.	Reddish-pink.	9.89 9.79 p.c.
7. Fluorenone-2-(2')-azo-1'-hydroxy-naphthalene-4'-sulphonic acid.	D + 1-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid.	Reddish-violet (hot alcohol); m.p. above 310°.	Slightly soluble in water, moderately in hot alcohol and hot benzene.	Deep scarlet.	6.82 6.51 "
8. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-4'-diethylaminobenzene.	D + diethylaniline.	Deep brown crystalline powder (hot alcohol); m.p. above 310°.	Soluble in hot alcohol, hot benzene or hot acetone, insoluble in water.	Yellowish-brown.	11.9 11.83 "
9. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-2'-naphthol-4':6'-disulphonic acid.	D + R-acid (2-naphthol-3:6-disulphonic acid).	Brownish-red crystalline powder (hot alcohol); m.p. above 310°.	Moderately soluble in water, soluble in much alcohol.	Brownish-red.	5.75 5.49 "
10. Fluorenone-2-(1')-azo-2'-naphthol-6':8'-disulphonic acid.	D + G-acid (2-naphthol-6:8-disulphonic acid).	Deep scarlet red crystalline powder (hot alcohol); m.p. above 310°.	Moderately soluble in water, slightly in acetone, soluble in hot alcohol.	Dyeing properties unsatisfactory.	5.92 5.49 "

TABLE C.

Fluorenonylamide Derivatives.

Name.	Method of preparation. { A + 2-aminofluorenone.	Analysis (nitrogen).	
		Found.	Calc.
1. 2-Oxalylaminofluorenone (oxal-di-2-fluorenonylamide).	A + oxalyl chloride.	5.55	6.3 p.c.
2. 2-Phthalylaminofluorenone (phthalal-di-2-fluorenonyl amide).	A + phthalyl chloride.	5.79	5.38 "
3. 2-Carbonylamino fluorenone (2-difluorenonyl carbamide).	A + carbonyl chloride (toluene solution).	6.99	6.73 "
4. 2-Thiocarbonylamino fluorenone (2-difluorenyl thiocarbamide).	A + thionyl chloride.	6.83	6.42 "
5. 2-Malonaminofluorenone (malon-di-2-fluorenonyl amide).	A + malonic acid and phosphorus pentachloride.	6.38	6.4 "
6. 2-Succinaminofluorenone (succin-di-2-fluorenonyl amide).	A + succinic acid and phosphorus pentachloride.	6.27	5.93 "
7. 2-Glutaraminofluorenone (glutar-di-2-fluorenonyl amide).	A + glutaric acid and phosphorus pentachloride.	5.96	5.76 "

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received, July 13, 1931.

